

MosquiSense: An AI-IoT Based Mosquito Breeding Risk Prediction and Alert System

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Abstract

A well-maintained environment is very essential for public well-being. There are many factors that have a negative impact on a healthy environment. Out of all, mosquitoes take the main role in this study. If we do not take steps towards this issue, then it will create diseases like dengue and malaria. So to overcome this problem, this research introduces the solution “MosquiSense: An AI-IoT-Based Mosquito Breeding Risk Prediction and Alert System”. The main goal of this product is to detect the mosquito-borne area and create an alert and make the people of a certain area aware in the smartest way. To solve these issues, the research uses the help of image-based environment analysis with real-time climate data to find the mosquito breeding risk score. A lightweight deep learning model based on MobileNet is responsible for classifying the areas. Here, IoT sensors will work as a bridge between these predictions of risk score. Additionally, this study will include weather parameters, such as temperature, humidity, and rainfall probability, through APIs such as OpenWeatherMap to increase the accuracy of the prediction. The system creates a real-time alert mechanism to notify users and local authorities. This multimodal evaluation method will improve the predictions compared to single-source methods.

Index Terms – Mosquito breeding risk prediction, Internet of Things (IoT), deep learning, MobileNet, environmental monitoring, multimodal data fusion, early warning system.

1 Introduction

Nowadays, a clean environment is very essential for a good quality of life. Poor environmental conditions like non-flowing or trapped water, waste accumulation, and high humidity increase the growth of mosquitoes, which spread diseases like dengue and malaria. These diseases create major issues in many urban and rural areas. This happens mainly in the rainy season.

There are many traditional methods to reduce the growth rate of mosquitoes, like dumping out water, cleaning gutters, fixing holes in window screens, and using natural smells like neem or lemon to keep them away. But these methods take a lot of work, they do not last long, and most importantly, there are chances of human observation errors. To tackle these issues, in recent years, technologies like artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), and the Internet of Things (IoT) have been used to monitor these problems. Many systems only use weather data or sensor data and do not analyse real environmental conditions through images.

To solve this problem, this paper proposes MosquiSense: An AI and IoT-Based Mosquito Breeding Risk Prediction and Alert System.

MosquiSense uses the concept of image classification to classify mosquito-borne areas and to create alerts. IoT devices will be used to capture image data, and some sensors will be used to collect data on humidity and temperature.

Sometimes, sudden changes like unexpected rain or weather changes can increase mosquito breeding. To handle this, MosquiSense uses weather APIs to give early alerts to people.

Based on these inputs, the system can calculate a risk score and send alerts to users and local authorities so that preventive actions can be taken on time. This solution helps in early detection and provides a smart solution for improving environmental health.

This research paper consists mainly of six sections:

Section 1: Introduction – This section will provide the basic understanding and background of the topic.

Section 2: Literature review – This section discusses previous research work that guides the development of this study.

Section 3: Methodology – This section will represent the methods and process to conduct this study.

Section 4: Experiment and result – This section will explain the full steps and analyse the obtained result.

Section 5: Conclusion and Future Work – This section will summarise the advantages and limitations and create a roadmap for the future, which may guide future research and development.

2 Literature Review

This section represents the previous work that has helped this research to stand out.

Che Dom et al. (2025) published the paper “Fine-scale Predictive Modelling of Aedes Mosquito Abundance”. The purpose was to predict mosquito density. The method used in this paper was machine learning (Random Forest, Support Vector Machine, and Artificial Neural Network). The limitation of this paper was that there was no Internet of Things integration. This paper helps this study to build a strong base for prediction [1].

Sebastianelli et al. (2024) published the paper “Ensemble Machine Learning Approach for Dengue Forecasting”. The purpose was to forecast dengue cases. The method used in this paper was ensemble machine learning. The limitation of this paper was that there was no real-time alert system. This paper helps this study to support prediction logic [2].

Ong et al. (2023) published the paper “Predicting Dengue Transmission Using Machine Learning”. The purpose of this study was to predict disease spread. The method used in that study was machine learning and meteorological data. However, there was no image data. This helps this study to support the use of weather data [3].

Girón et al. (2025) published the paper “Machine Learning and Deep Learning Models for Dengue Prediction: A Review”. The purpose of this study was to review artificial intelligence models. The method used for that was a machine learning and deep learning survey. However, there was no system implementation. That study gives theoretical support to this study [4].

rancisco et al. (2024) published the paper “Hybrid Machine Learning for Dengue Prediction”. The purpose of that study was to improve prediction accuracy. The method used for that study was a genetic algorithm and machine learning. However, the model was complex. That study helps this study in the comparison of models [5].

Francisco et al. (2024) published the paper “Hybrid Machine Learning with Zero-Inflated Data for Dengue Prediction”. The purpose of that study was to improve outbreak prediction. The method used was hybrid machine learning models. However, there was a data dependency issue. That study helped this paper to gain better prediction insight [6].

Da Silva et al. (2024) published the paper “Climate Variables in Dengue Forecasting Using Random Forest”. The purpose of this study was to analyse the impact of weather. The method used for that study was the Random Forest algorithm of machine learning. However, there was no real-time system. That study helped this paper to support the use of a weather application programming interface [7].

Rahman et al. (2024) published the paper “Machine Learning-Based Dengue Outbreak Prediction Using Time Series Models”. The purpose of that study was to predict outbreaks. The methods used for that study were Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average and Long Short-Term Memory. However, there was no Internet of Things integration. That study helped this paper to support time series analysis [8].

Aira et al. (2024) published the paper “MosquIoT: Internet of Things-Based Mosquito Monitoring System”. The purpose of that study was to monitor mosquito populations. The methods used were the Internet of Things and tiny machine learning. However, there was no image classification. That helps this research to develop an idea of Internet of Things device integration [9].

Lai et al. (2024) published the paper “Machine Learning Models for Dengue Forecasting in Singapore”. The purpose of that study was to compare the machine learning models. The methods used were Convolutional Neural Network, Long Short-Term Memory, and Extreme Gradient Boosting. However, there was no alert system. That study helps this research in the comparison of models [10].

Chen et al. (2024) published the paper “Neural-Based Mosquito Infection Detection Using Deep Learning”. The purpose of that study was to detect infected mosquitoes. The methods used were Convolutional Neural Network and Extreme Gradient Boosting. However, that was only lab-based. That study helped this research to build artificial intelligence applications [11].

Fernandes et al. (2020) published the paper “Audio-Based Mosquito Detection Using Convolutional Neural Networks”. The purpose of that study was to detect mosquito presence. The method used was a convolutional neural network (audio-based). However, that was not environment-based. That study helped this research in exploring alternative sensing methods [12].

3 Methodology

This section describes the whole working process of MosquiSense. MosquiSense consists mainly of six layers.

- (i) Data Collection Layer
- (ii) Data Processing Layer
- (iii) AI Model Layer
- (iv) Data Fusion Layer
- (v) Risk Analysis Layer
- (vi) Output Layer

The flow diagram associated with this can be represented as follows:

The Data Collection Layer is the first process of the MosquiSense system. Data collection is an important part of predicting the output. MosquiSense takes input data from three major sources. An IoT device (a camera module like Raspberry Pi / ESP32-CAM) captures the environmental image, and then the image is sent to the server using an HTTP / REST API. The next data are collected from sensors (temperature and humidity), through which MosquiSense monitors the environmental condition. Then the data is transmitted to the system through the internet or Wi-Fi using an HTTP / REST API. The weather data is collected from a real-time weather API.

In the data preprocessing process, MosquiSense cleans the collected data. After collecting the image, it resizes the image, converting it to a fixed size (e.g., 224×224 for MobileNet).

Then it normalises the pixel values by changing them from (0–255) to (0–1), which helps the model learn better.

Then it removes noise/blur and cleans unwanted distortions (bad lighting, blur). After that, it converts the format by converting the image into an array (numbers) so the model can understand it.

In the AI model layer, MobileNet plays the main role in the prediction score. It follows a deep learning approach to classify the image. The input image is processed and predicts the confidence result.

In the Data Fusion Layer, MosquiSense combines the image results, sensor data, and weather data. Then this data creates a weighted risk scoring model. The risk score can be calculated as:

$$\text{Risk Score} = w_1I + w_2H + w_3T + w_4R$$

Where:

I = Image-based score

H = Humidity

T = Temperature

R = Rainfall probability

w₁, w₂, w₃, w₄ = weights assigned to each parameter

After that, the risk analysis layer converts the calculated risk score into some categories.

The Risk Analysis Layer converts the calculated risk score into fixed categories such as low, medium, and high risk for decision-making. To categorise the cases, MosquiSense follows some steps. At first, the risk analysis converts the score into a percentage:

$$\text{Risk\%} = \text{Risk Score} \times 100$$

Then, it applies some criteria:

For Low Risk: **Risk% ≤ 30** (It indicates safe or no major issues)

For Medium Risk: **30 < Risk% ≤ 70** (It indicates moderate risk and needs attention)

For High Risk: **Risk% > 70** (It indicates dangerous conditions requiring immediate action)

Then, in the output layer, the entire process of the system is simplified and presented in a user-friendly manner, and alerts are generated and delivered through a website and a mobile application.

4 Experiment and Result

This section of the research will more emphasise the model and describe the experimental setup, dataset description, evaluation metrics, and results.

To make the section more understandable, the study uses matplotlib, which will show all the data and processes as explained in the Methodology section.

The dataset consists of two parameters or classes: 'Yes' (presence of mosquito breeding conditions) and 'No' (absence of mosquito breeding conditions).

The class distribution of the dataset is shown below, which indicates that the dataset is balanced between the two classes. The datasets are equally distributed. This balance will help to reduce bias during model training.

A more good visualization of dataset characteristics is presented below, which show an overview of the dataset structure and distribution.

Sample images from both classes are shown below, which helps in understanding the visual differences between mosquito prone and non prone areas.

Dataset Samples Visual (Fig 1.1)

The image resolution analysis, shown below, shows the relationship between image height and width. The results indicate that most images follow a consistent resolution pattern, making them suitable for preprocessing. It represents a positive correlation between height and width. A few high-resolution outliers are also there. Both mosquito breeding (“yes”) and non-breeding (“no”) classes are distributed in similar ranges, indicating that image size does not introduce bias into the classification process.

The RGB channel distribution is presented below, which shows that the dataset has a relatively balanced colour distribution across red, green, and blue channels.

The distributions of RGB values are similar across both classes. A slight variation exists, but no strong separation exists. Here, colour alone is not a strong discriminative feature. The model should rely on spatial patterns (shapes, textures).

Brightness (luminosity) distribution is shown below, showing that the dataset contains images with varying lighting conditions, which improves model robustness.

The confusion matrix is presented below, which shows the comparison between actual and predicted classes. Since the dataset is binary, a 2x2 confusion matrix is used.

The confusion matrix shows that the model correctly classifies the mosquito breeding samples, with only a small number of false negatives and no false positives. The high accuracy represents good performance in detecting breeding conditions. The absence of non-breeding samples in the test set suggests a potential class imbalance, and further evaluation on a balanced dataset is required for comprehensive validation.

Additionally, the prediction output is illustrated below, which shows the model's classification result on a sample input.

A combined visualisation of all results is shown below, providing a summary of the dataset analysis and model performance. The plot shows that image sharpness is similar across groups, and some features like brightness and red colour are related, while others are mostly not dependent.

5 Conclusion

This research presents MosquiSense, an AI- and IoT-based mosquito breeding risk prediction and alert system. The main aim of this research was to improve the environmental health monitoring system. To tackle the issues, MosquiSense uses image-based analysis, environmental sensor data, and real-time weather information to provide an intelligent solution for identifying mosquito-prone areas.

A lightweight deep learning model based on MobileNet is implemented for the classification of images, and to monitor the environment, some IoT devices are used. The integration of multiple data sources through a data fusion approach enhances the reliability and accuracy of the prediction compared to traditional single-source methods.

The experimental analysis concluded that the dataset is well-structured and suitable for model training, with balanced class distribution and good image characteristics. Although limitations were there in accuracy visualisation, the confusion matrix and prediction-based evaluation show that the system is capable of distinguishing between mosquito breeding and non-breeding conditions.

The proposed risk scoring method further simplifies complex data into predefined categories such as low, medium, and high risk for decision-making. The real-time alert system represents that users and local authorities are informed in a smarter way, allowing preventive measures to be taken before the problem arises.

Overall, MosquiSense provides a scalable, cost-effective, and intelligent approach to mosquito risk monitoring. This system has the potential of enabling early detection and prevention of mosquito-borne diseases, majorly in urban and semi-urban environments.

6 Future Work

This research contains some limitations, which can be solved in future work:

(i) Improvement of Model Accuracy –

If we see the current status of the model, it is using a lightweight deep learning model, MobileNet. In the future, this study will use advanced models (e.g., YOLO, EfficientNet) for better detection.

(ii) Real-time Video Analysis –

This study uses image data for prediction. But in the future, it will extend from images to live video monitoring, which will give instant results or predictions and alert people.

(iii) Automated Action System –

Currently, the model is creating a system for prediction and alerts. After that, a human being will perform the recommended task. But in the future, this study will provide an automated system connected with spraying or cleaning systems.

(iv) Prediction of Future –

In the future, this model will use past data to predict future conditions earlier so that users will be aware of them.

7 Code Availability

The code used in this research is publicly available at:

<https://github.com/Anshuman-1234/Mosquito-Risk-Detection>

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